

DEVELOPMENT AND UTILIZATION OF INTERACTIVE VIDEO-BASED CONTEXTUALIZED STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIALS IN GRADE 8 EARTH SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to address the low Science performance of students in the Division of Agusan del Sur by developing and utilizing interactive-based contextualized strategic intervention materials (CSIM) to enhance learning outcomes. The research employed a developmental and mixed-method approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data. The study involved 20 teacher validators, 5 expert validators, and 30 Grade 8 students to assess the quality and effectiveness of the developed material. Results revealed that the CSIM received highly satisfactory ratings from both teachers and experts, confirming their pedagogical value. Statistical analysis indicated a significant improvement in students' performance, as shown by a notable difference between pre-test and post-test scores, affirming the effectiveness of CSIM in addressing the least-learned competencies in Earth Science. Additionally, qualitative feedback emphasized the need for content enhancement through the incorporation of cultural elements and improvements in instructional and assessment quality. The study highlighted the potential of interactive and contextualized learning materials in addressing persistent challenges in science education and recommended further refinements for broader implementation.

Keywords: *Interactive-based Contextualized Strategic Intervention Material, Pre-test, Post-test, Teacher Validators, Expert Validators, Grade 8 students*

INTRODUCTION

Scientific education in the Philippines aimed to enhance students' scientific literacy, enabling them to become informed and engaged citizens capable of making decisions regarding the application of scientific knowledge in areas such as the environment, society, and health. However, recent results from the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA, 2022) revealed that almost no Filipino students were top performers in science (OECD, 2023). Similarly, the National Achievement Test (NAT) in 2018 further emphasized this issue, showing Science as the lowest-performing subject with an average score of 28.42%. These results underscored the urgent need to address the gaps in science education in the country.

In the Division of Agusan del Sur, student performance in Science remained a concern. Recent evaluations showed that the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) for the division during the second quarter of School Year 2022–2023 was 68.28, decreasing slightly to 67.22 in School Year 2023–2024. This trend indicated a persistent challenge in improving students' mastery of science competencies. Specifically, at Libertad National High School, the MPS in Science 8 exhibited a declining pattern, with scores of 63.18% in SY 2022–2023 and 61.97% in SY 2023–2024. Teachers' reports suggested that several competencies remained least mastered, including (1) explaining how movements along faults generate earthquakes (S8ES-IIa-14), (2) explaining how typhoons developed and how they were affected by landmasses and bodies of water (S8ES-IIf-21), and (3) comparing and contrasting comets, meteors, and asteroids (S8ES-IIg-22). The persistently low achievement rates in Science indicated the need for targeted interventions, as they reflected broader concerns about the quality of basic education. Among the identified contributing factors was the shortage of proficient teachers who served as the primary sources of knowledge in lieu of adequate books and learning materials.

The increasing number of least-learned competencies in the Science curriculum, particularly in schools within the Bunawan District, further underscored the urgency of addressing this issue. As the average MPS for Science in the division continued to remain at a moderate level, developing strategic intervention materials was identified as a potential solution to improve competency-based skills among students. In response, various interventions were implemented, including Contextualized Strategic Intervention Materials (CSIM). Contextualization was recognized as a crucial strategy for engaging learners by allowing them to relate their lessons to real-life experiences (Reyes et al., 2019). Studies indicated that utilizing the scaffolding technique within CSIM significantly enhanced students' competence (Ai Aila & Keshta, 2015).

Despite these efforts, challenges persisted in effectively contextualizing interactive discussions and activities, highlighting a gap in the development of more engaging and comprehensive instructional materials. Existing literature suggested that while contextualized learning strategies showed promise, there remained a lack of research on their implementation in digital and video-based formats, particularly in Science education (Payot & Deloy, 2022). With this, a form of remediation to increase the academic

achievement of low-performing learners needed to be developed to address the low competencies in schools (De Jesus, 2019). Addressing this research gap, the present study sought to develop interactive video-based contextualized strategic intervention materials for Grade 8 Science, aligned with the K to 12 Curriculum of the Department of Education.

By integrating interactive and contextualized instructional materials, this study aimed to enhance students' mastery of key Science competencies. The researchers of this study sought to provide a practical solution that not only improved learning outcomes but also fostered meaningful engagement by incorporating students' environmental contexts, prior experiences, and cognitive frameworks into instructional materials (Adonis, 2020). Given the observed decline in Science MPS, the timeliness and relevance of this study were evident. The findings contributed to the growing body of literature on contextualized education while addressing a pressing educational challenge in the Division of Agusan del Sur.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the least learned competencies of grade 8 students in Science?
2. What is the quality of interactive video-based contextualized strategic intervention materials as evaluated by teachers and experts in terms of:
 - 2.1.content;
 - 2.2.format;
 - 2.3.presentation and organization; and
 - 2.4.accuracy and up-to-datedness?
3. Is there a significant difference between the evaluation of teachers and experts on CSIM's quality?
4. What are the mean gain scores of Grades 8 students in Science?
5. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the students?
6. What are the overall comments/feedback made by the students, teachers and experts on the developed interactive video-based contextualized strategic intervention materials?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The research was conducted in a selected public secondary school in Agusan del Sur. The selection of the target school was purposive, as it represented a typical public school in the municipality based on performance and size. The researcher chose this school due to familiarity with the institution and a commitment to developing Interactive Video-Based Contextualized Strategic Intervention Materials to support students in the area. Additionally, the school's rural location in the Caraga region presented an

opportunity to explore how technological innovations could be integrated into science education.

Research Respondents and Sampling Method

The study involved validators from different educational backgrounds as well as student participants. The respondents were selected using purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique that involved carefully identifying and selecting individuals with relevant expertise and experience in relation to the study (Creswell & Clark, 2017). The respondents included:

- **Teacher Validators:** Twenty (20) Grade 8 Science teachers from different schools evaluated the instructional quality of the developed CSIM.
- **Expert Validators:** Five (5) experts, including master teachers and Education Program Supervisors (EPS) in Science, assessed the instructional quality and effectiveness of the CSIM.
- **Grade 8 Students:** Thirty (30) students participated as primary beneficiaries of the CSIM. These students had access to digital devices necessary for using the developed material.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first obtained permission from the school administration to conduct the study. Upon approval, the researcher identified the least-learned competencies in Grade 8 Science based on school records. These competencies served as the basis for developing the CSIM.

The instructional material underwent validation by teacher and expert validators, who provided feedback using the assessment rating sheet. After revisions were made, the CSIM was implemented in a Grade 8 Science class.

Students were given a pre-test before using the CSIM. The implementation phase involved students engaging with the instructional materials, followed by a post-test to measure improvements in their performance. After the intervention, students answered perception questionnaires, and select participants participated in semi-structured interviews to provide qualitative insights.

Research Instruments

This study used different types of instruments, which were described as follows:

The assessment rating sheet that was utilized in this study was based on the Department of Education Guidelines and Processes for LRMS Assessment and Evaluation of Localized Materials. The purpose of the tool in this study was to determine the level of instructional quality of the material. The level of instructional quality was designed to evaluate the Contextualized Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) in terms of

content, format, presentation and organization, and accuracy and up-to-datedness of information.

The table below showed the mean ranges per factor in the evaluation rating sheet and their corresponding description and interpretation that were used in this study, while the next part of the evaluation tool provided the qualitative ratings on whether the interactive video-based contextualized strategic intervention materials developed were recommended for reproduction and distribution, and whether these resources were acceptable.

Table 1. Four-point Likert Scale used to assess the Level of Instructional Quality of CSIM

Rate	Mean Rating	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4	3.26-4.00	Very Satisfactory	This means that the item exceeds expectations with no revisions needed.
3	2.51-3.25	Satisfactory	This means that the item meets expectations with minimal revision needed.
2	1.76-2.50	Poor	This means that the item below exceeds expectations with maximum revision needed.
1	1.00-1.75	Not Satisfactory	This means that the item did not meet the expectations and the SIMs will be discarded.

Furthermore, self-made perception questionnaires were used to describe the learners' perceptions of certain ways in which the developed CSIM helped the students in understanding the concepts, the things that they liked in the CSIM, and the difficulties they encountered, as well as the things they wanted to improve in doing/using the Contextualized SIM. Three (3) open-ended questions were utilized, allowing the respondents to freely express their opinions in English, Filipino, the vernacular, or any combination of these languages.

Moreover, the researcher-made achievement test was used in the study, which underwent pilot and validity tests by Science teachers. A twenty-five (25) item multiple-choice test for the pre-test and post-test covered the contents of the least learned competencies. The tests underwent pilot testing before the implementation, and revisions were made accordingly. The thesis adviser also validated the utilized test. The test was designed to measure prior knowledge and learners' performance in the subject matter.

Data Analysis

The qualitative data obtained from the respondents involved the utilization of coding. Following the transcription process, the researcher aimed to identify the experiences and challenges of the students regarding the utilization of the material. The researcher utilized thematic analysis to discern the occurring, interesting, and relevant themes present in the collected data. Thematic analysis was a research methodology used to identify, analyze, organize, describe, and report on the themes that emerged from the collected data (Braun and Clarke, 2016).

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical procedures were used to analyze the data collected for this study:

The selection of least-learned competencies was determined using frequency count and percentage.

The instructional quality of the CSIM was analyzed using mean scores from the assessment rating sheet.

The significant difference in teacher and expert evaluations was analyzed using the Mann-Whitney test.

To measure the effect of the CSIM on student performance, pre-test and post-test scores were compared using a Paired T-test.

Scope and Limitations

The study focused on developing and evaluating an Interactive Video-Based Contextualized Strategic Intervention Material for Grade 8 Science. The research was limited to the second quarter of the school year and specifically addressed the least-learned competencies in Earth Science.

The sample size was limited to 30 students, 20 teacher validators, and 5 expert validators, which may not be representative of all Grade 8 learners. The study also depended on students having access to digital devices to interact with the CSIM, which could affect implementation in areas with limited technological resources. Additionally, while the instructional material was designed for long-term use, the study only measured its short-term impact. Further research is needed to examine its effectiveness over extended periods and across different contexts.

DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the distribution of teachers who identified the three least learned competencies (LLCs) in Grade 8 Science. The competencies include:

1. LLC Code S8ES-IIa-14 – Explaining how movements along faults generate earthquakes.
2. LLC Code S8ES-IIf-21 – Describing how a typhoon develops and how it is affected by landmasses and bodies of water.
3. LLC Code S8ES-IIg-22 – Comparing and contrasting comets, meteors, and asteroids.

Studies by Estacio & Cornejo (2021) and Mijares (2023) suggest that students face challenges in mastering Earth Science topics due to unfamiliar terminology and complex concepts. To address these difficulties, they recommend using interactive learning methods, enhanced vocabulary instruction, and scaffolded learning techniques to improve comprehension.

Table 2. List of Least Learned Competencies for the Second Quarter

LLC Code	Competency
(S8ES-IIa-14)	Explain how movements along faults generate earthquakes.
(S8ES-IIf-21)	Explain how a typhoon develops and how it is affected by landmasses and bodies of water.
(S8ES-IIg-22)	Compare and contrast comets, meteors, and asteroids.

Quality of Interactive Video-Based Contextualized Strategic Intervention Materials (CSIM)

1. Content

Table 3 presents the evaluation results for the CSIM's content quality. Teachers rated the content with an average score of $M = 3.79$, $SD = 0.42$, while experts rated it $M = 3.80$, $SD = 0.45$, both describing it as very satisfactory. Both teachers and experts agree that the material can effectively help develop students' Science competencies.

Teachers particularly rated content accuracy ($M = 3.95$, $SD = 0.23$) as the highest aspect. However, item 8, "Content is relevant to real-life situations," received the lowest mean rating from teachers, 3.63 ($SD = 0.83$). Similarly, experts rated this item with a mean score of 3.80 ($SD = 0.45$). These ratings indicate that the CSIM content is considered highly relevant to real-life situations, with a very satisfactory evaluation. Teachers unanimously agreed that the material is highly effective in enhancing students' ability to apply their learning in real-life contexts.

Table 3. Evaluation on interactive video-based contextualized strategic intervention materials in terms of Content

	TEACHER			EXPERT		
	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D
1. Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepED Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	3.79	0.41	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
2. Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	3.69	0.59	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
3. Content is accurate.	3.95	0.23	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
4. Content is up-to-date.	3.89	0.32	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
5. Content is logically developed and organized.	3.74	0.65	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
6. Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	3.74	0.56	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
7. Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3.64	0.6	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
8. Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.63	0.83	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
9. Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	3.74	0.45	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
10. Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	3.74	0.56	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
	3.79	0.42	VS	3.80	0.45	VS

Legend: D - Description NS - Not Satisfactory P - Poor S - Satisfactory VS – Very Satisfactory

2. Format

Table 4 shows the evaluation of the CSIM's format. Teachers rated it M = 3.59, SD = 0.12, while experts rated it M = 3.64, SD = 0.35, both describing it as very satisfactory.

Both teachers and experts agree that the material is highly effective in developing students' Science competencies. However, engagement and creativity received relatively lower scores, with teachers rating “Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging” at $M = 3.53$, $SD = 0.70$, and experts rating “Material effectively stimulates creativity” at $M = 3.20$, $SD = 1.30$ indicating room for enhancement. The ratings describe the format of the material as satisfactory. These described the potential of the CSIM to develop engaging qualities from the students.

Table 4. Evaluation on interactive video-based contextualized strategic intervention materials in terms of format

	TEACHER		VS	EXPERT		
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. Purpose of the material is well defined.	3.74	0.56	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
2. Material achieves its defined purpose.	3.68	0.67	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
3. Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	3.58	0.77	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
4. Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	3.68	0.58	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
5. Graphics / colors / sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.68	0.48	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
6. Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	3.53	0.70	VS	3.00	1.22	S
7. Material effectively stimulates creativity of the target user.	3.53	0.84	VS	3.20	1.30	S
8. Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	3.42	0.83	VS	3.60	0.89	VS
9. Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	3.53	0.77	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
10. Instruction is integrated with the target user's previous experience.	3.53	0.78	VS	3.80	0.45	VS

	3.59	0.12	VS	3.64	0.35	VS
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Legend: D - Description NS - Not Satisfactory P - Poor S - Satisfactory VS - Very Satisfactory

3. Presentation and Organization

Table 5 presents the results on CSIM's presentation and organization. Teachers rated it $M = 3.75$, $SD = 0.51$, while experts rated it $M = 3.77$, $SD = 0.15$, both describing it as very satisfactory. Experts provided uniform mean ratings ($M = 3.80$, $SD = 0.45$) across multiple areas, suggesting that the material is logically structured and visually engaging.

Table 5. Evaluation on interactive video-based contextualized strategic intervention materials in terms of presentation and organization

	TEACHER			EXPERT		
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. Audio enhances understanding of the concept.	3.84	0.37	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
2. Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood.	3.89	0.31	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
3. There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any.	3.79	0.54	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
4. Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	3.84	0.50	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
5. Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	3.89	0.32	VS	3.60	0.89	VS
6. Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	3.74	0.45	VS	3.80	0.45	VS

7. Visuals sustain interest and do not distract user's attention.	3.74	0.56	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
8. Visuals provide accurate representation of the concept discussed.	3.74	0.56	VS	3.60	0.89	VS
9. The user support materials (if any) are effective.	3.68	0.75	VS	3.60	0.89	VS
10. The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material.	3.68	0.58	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
11. The material can easily and independently be used.	3.68	0.58	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
12. The material will run using minimum system requirements.	3.89	0.46	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
13. The program is free from technical problems.	3.89	0.46	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
	3.75	0.51	VS	3.77	0.15	VS

Legend: *D* - Description *NS* - Not Satisfactory *P* - Poor *S* - Satisfactory *VS* – Very Satisfactory

4. Accuracy and Up-to-datedness

Table 6 presents the evaluation results for accuracy and up-to-datedness. Teachers rated it $M = 3.53$, $SD = 0.77$, while experts rated it $M = 3.80$, $SD = 0.77$, both describing it as very satisfactory. These entail that the material is very satisfactory when it comes to freedom from errors and update on information used.

Table 6. Evaluation on interactive video-based contextualized strategic intervention materials in terms of accuracy and up-to-datedness

	TEACHER			EXPERT		
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	

1. Conceptual errors.	3.53	0.77	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
2. Factual errors.	3.53	0.77	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
3. Grammatical and / or typographical errors.	3.53	0.77	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
4. Other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visuals, etc.).	3.53	0.77	VS	3.80	0.45	VS
	3.53	0.77	VS	3.8	0.77	VS

Legend: D - Description NS - Not Satisfactory P - Poor S - Satisfactory VS - Very Satisfactory

Significant Differences in the Evaluation of Teachers and Experts

Comparing teacher and expert evaluations of CSIM quality across four factors yielded significant differences in content ($U=20.0$, $p=0.023$) and accuracy/up-to-datedness ($U=10.0$, $p=0.008$), leading to the rejection of null hypotheses. However, no significant differences were found in format ($U=24.0$, $p=0.052$) and presentation/organization ($U=70$, $p=0.479$), so their null hypotheses were accepted.

Teachers emphasized that learning materials should consider students' diverse backgrounds, beliefs, and cultural influences, enhancing engagement and bridging home and classroom experiences. Additionally, they suggested adding further reading resources to improve accuracy and relevance. Research supports the importance of quality learning materials in promoting effective teaching, especially in resource-limited settings. Experts and researchers play a key role in ensuring intervention materials enhance the learning process.

Table 7. Significant difference between the evaluation of teachers and experts on CSIM's quality

Factor	U	p-value	Decision
Content	20.0	.023	Rejected
Format	24.0	.052	Not Rejected
Presentation and Organization	70.0	.479	Not Rejected
Accuracy and Up-to-datedness	10.0	.008	Rejected

Pre-Test and Post-Test Results

Based on Table 8, the mean pretest score of the learners was 7.33. The achievement level of the learners in pre-test was in the developing proficient level. Moreover, the coefficient of variation in the pretest implies that the scores of the learners were scattered. Now in terms of the post-test results, the mean score is 11.33. Based on the coefficient of variation, the post-test scores of the learners were consistent around the mean. Moreover, the verbal interpretation for the post-test mean score was approaching proficient. It means that the learners improved from developing proficient level to approaching proficient level. Therefore, it implies that there was a visible improvement among the learners. The result confirms the findings of Keller & Zwilling (2016) when compared to students who used standard textbook approaches, biology students who watched instructional videos exhibited a greater understanding of the material, which improved retention and resulted in higher post-test scores.

Table 8. Pre-test and post-test mean scores of Grade 8 students in Science

Descriptive Statistics	Mean Gain Score	Standard Deviation	Gain Score Interpretation
Pre-test	7.33	3.36	Low Increase
Post-test	11.33	3.14	Average Increase

Significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the students

Table 9 shows the significance difference of pre-test and post-test with a P value of 0.000. Hence, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the learners during the pre-test and post-test. Furthermore, since there is a significant difference between pre-test and post-test this means that there was an improvement in terms of the performance of the learners utilizing the microlearning videos.

This result of the study confirms the findings of Lalian (2018) who stipulated that videos were used as a learning medium in teaching. Based on the result, he concluded that videos play a vital role in improving learners' motivation in learning, enhancing their knowledge and understanding of the lesson, and in improving their achievements. Moreover, one local study published by Ladrillo (2021), stated that learners who were exposed to teacher – made learning videos performed significantly better and obtained high mean score than those learners who were not.

Table 9. Significance of Difference Between Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores

Descriptive Statistics	T value	P value	Decision
Pre-test and Post-test Scores	-6.302	.000	Significant

Feedback on Interactive Video-Based Contextualized Strategic Intervention Materials

Improvement of Instructional and Assessment Quality

Participants highlighted key areas for enhancement in the instructional and assessment aspects of the materials:

- Limited interactive features in discussions
- Need for more motivational activities
- Lack of structured and diverse assessments

Respondents emphasized the importance of interactive elements, aligning with Barnett-Itzhaki et al. (2023) and Connolly (2024), who stress their role in engaging diverse learning styles. The need for motivational activities is supported by Motevalli et al. (2020), which highlights the role of stimulating content in sustaining student interest. Additionally, Paolini (2015) underscores the necessity of varied assessments to accurately measure learning progress.

Grounded in Social Constructivist Theory, this study recommends incorporating diverse assessments and interactive features to better address students' learning needs.

Enhancement of Content Quality

Experts and validators identified areas for content improvement:

- Lack of cultural relevance
- Unclear learning objectives
- Limited interactive elements

Cultural relevance is crucial, as Dee & Penner (2016) found it improves academic performance. Danis (2017) highlights the importance of clear learning objectives in engaging students effectively. Moreover, Kobayashi (2018) stresses that interactive teaching methods, such as peer collaboration, enhance critical thinking and engagement.

Rooted in Culturally Responsive Teaching (CRT) as discussed by Vavrus (2008), this study suggests integrating culturally relevant content, refining learning objectives, and incorporating interactive elements to foster better student engagement and learning outcomes.

Table 10. Key Areas for Enhancing Instructional and Content Quality in Video-Based Learning Materials.

Themes	Core Ideas
Improvement of Instructional and Assessment Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited element of interactive features in the discussion • More motivational activities • Absence of structured and diverse assessment
Enhancement of Content Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of cultural relevance in the content • Objectives are not clear • Less interactive elements in the discussion

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Following the ADDIE Model in developing the CSIM, learners were able to have better scores after the implementation of the material. Hence, the CSIM passed all the factors in the evaluation rating sheet, including content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and other factors. It also passed all indicators of technical aspects. These indicate that the CSIM are acceptable and appropriate and are highly recommended to be used in Grade 8 Science classes.

2. There was a significant difference between the pretest scores and post-test scores of the learners. This implies that their performance improved while utilizing the CSIM material.

3. CSIM helped the learners to expand their knowledge on the topic because its short, bite-sized contents were more focused; learners were not overwhelmed by information. However, validators made it clear that when designing learning experiences, we must consider the diverse backgrounds, beliefs, and cultural influences of our learners. This includes their family history, personal experiences, and the myths and cultural norms they may hold. they also wished to have more contextualized examples and more clear objectives.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Science teachers may develop video-based instructional materials using the ADDIE model. Videos should be short (i.e., less than 10 minutes), include

contextualized examples, clearly present lessons and objectives, and consider learners' diverse backgrounds.

2. CSIM should be used to enhance student mastery of least-learned competencies in Grade 8 Science, as it has proven effective in improving performance.
3. School administrators may use these findings to support teachers in designing video-based materials as part of school improvement plans.
4. Future research may:
 - a. Extend the study duration for more comprehensive testing.
 - b. Include a control group for comparison to strengthen findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers adhered to ethical standards from the study's inception to its completion, following the guidelines set by the University. Prior to data collection, participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, goals, and objectives. Informed consent was obtained through a formal letter of permission, ensuring that participants were aware of their rights. They were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. Anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained, ensuring that any shared information remained private and was used solely for research purposes.

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